

How to change the R programme to do phylogenetic MCMCglmm to do the 4 analyses (2 sexes, 2 light environments)

(this is the only part which needs to be altered)

Put in one of these two contrast file names here

- ScaledStatsOpenCloudy.csv
- ScaledStatsNatural.csv

```
> #read in the data
> x<-read.csv("ScaledStats0openCloudy.csv")
>
> #prepare the data
> if(sum(is.na(x$JetzNames)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$JetzNames)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$Sources)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$Sources)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$Habitat)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$Habitat)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$HDensity)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$HDensity)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$SchOpen)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$SchOpen)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$ForageStyle)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$ForageStyle)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$TrophicLevel)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$TrophicLevel)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$Migration)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$Migration)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$ScMigrt)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$ScMigrt)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$Phenology)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$Phenology)),]}
> #if(sum(is.na(x$PhenologyCDE)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$PhenologyCDE)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$ScPheno)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$ScPheno)),]}
>
> if(sum(is.na(x$MaxLumF)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$MaxLumF)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$MinLumF)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$MinLumF)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$GmeanLF)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$GmeanLF)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$GsdLF)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$GsdLF)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$MnCrF)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$MnCrF)),]}
> if(sum(is.na(x$SDCrF)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$SDCrF)),]} #note: f & m not F & M these two vars
> if(sum(is.na(x$HueSDf)>0)){x<-x[-which(is.na(x$HueSDf)),]} # due to inconsistency in data
headings
> x$diffF=x$MaxLumF-x$MinLumF
> # hist(diff)
>
> x$zMaxLumF<-scale(x$MaxLumF)
> x$zMinLumF<-scale(x$MinLumF)
> x$zGmeanLF<-scale(x$GmeanLF)
> x$zGsdLF<-scale(x$GsdLF)
> x$zMnCrF<-scale(x$MnCrF)
> x$zSDCrF<-scale(sqrt(x$SDCrF)) #note names: SDCr HueSD m & f not M & F
> x$zHueSDf<-scale(x$HueSDf) #not ideal, with left skew
> x$zdiffF<-scale(sqrt(x$diffF)) #sqrt because goes to zero
>
> #read in the tree
> t100<-read.tree("tree0099full.tre")
>
```

This file is for females, for analysis of males change F→M and f→m

This R programme takes 8 hours (slower or faster depending upon your computer) because it is doing Bayesian MCMC. Here are the 4 outputs for the combinations of sex and light environment copied from the console output after running it.:

- ResultsOCLightMales.txt
- ResultsOCLightFemales.txt
- ResultsNaturalLightMales.txt
- ResultsNaturalLightFemales.txt